

CODECO

Cognitive Decentralised
Edge Cloud Orchestration

CARG **CODECO AI Resilience and Governance Toolkit**

White paper

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Executive Summary

This white paper explores the **CODECO CARG Toolkit**, which comprises an Artificial Intelligence (AI) resilience and governance methodological framework to assess the use and impact of AI in the **Kubernetes Cognitive Decentralised Edge Cloud (CODECO)** framework and in selected use-cases.

CARG is under development and validation within the Horizon Europe CODECO project to support AI-driven orchestration in Cloud-Edge environments.

The white paper explains **CARG** and its core principles. Drawing on established frameworks such as the EU AI Act, OECD Principles, and UNESCO's Ethics of Artificial Intelligence, **CARG** prioritizes transparency, replicability, and trustworthiness in its approach. Additionally, the white paper introduces advanced tools and processes to automate the assessment, monitoring, and improvement of AI in CODECO serving as blueprint for other similar initiatives.

This white paper focuses on explaining the CODECO AI resilience and governance framework and how it is being applied in the project, as a blueprint that can be adopted by other similar projects, offering practical strategies and innovations to address the challenges and opportunities of AI resilience and governance in Cloud-Edge ecosystems.

Keywords: AI/ML; governance; resilience; Edge-Cloud.

Disclaimer

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List of Acronyms

Acronym	Meaning
ACM	Automated Configuration Management
AI	Artificial Intelligence
AI Act	Artificial Intelligence Act
AIA	Artificial Intelligence Act
AJL	Algorithmic Justice League
ALTAI	Assessment List for Trustworthy Artificial Intelligence
AR	Academia and Research
AR	CODECO stakeholder group Academia and Research
CARG	CODECO AI Resilience and Governance framework
CEI	Cloud-Edge-IoT
CLAIRE	Confederation of Laboratories for Artificial Intelligence Research in Europe
CODECO	Cognitive Decentralised Edge-Cloud Orchestration
CPU	Central Processing Unit
DEV	CODECO stakeholder group developers
EUS	End-user, citizen
EUS	CODECO stakeholder group end-user
FMTI	Stanford Foundational Model Transparency Index
GA	Grant Agreement
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
GNN	Spatio-Temporal Graph Neural Network
GOV	Government, policy makers
GOV	CODECO stakeholder group policy makers
HE	Horizon Europe
HLEG	High-level Expert Group
HRESIA	Human Rights, Ethical and Social Impact Assessment
ICT	CODECO stakeholder group Industry and SMEs with focus on Information and Communication Technologies
IRCEP	Innovation Research and Community Engagement Programme
K8s	Kubernetes
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
LIME	Local Interpretable Model-agnostic Explanations
Mx	Month x of CODECO
MARL	Multi-agent Reinforcement Learning Model
ML	Machine Learning
MNIST	Modified National Institute of Standards and Technology database
MSx	Project Milestone, where x defines the identifier of the milestone
NetMA	Network Management and Adaptation
OSI	Open Systems Interconnection
OSS	Open-source Software
PAI	Partnership on AI

Acronym	Meaning
PDLC	Privacy-preserving Decentralised Learning
QoE	Quality of Experience
QoE	Quality of Experience
SDO	Standardisation Development Organisation
SWM	Seamless Workload Migration
TEF	Testing and Experimentation Facilities
XAI	Explainable AI

1 Introduction

Artificial Intelligence (AI) has emerged as a key enabler for managing the complexity of modern Cloud-Edge ecosystems, where distributed infrastructures and heterogeneous data require advanced orchestration solutions. Within this context, the CODECO project develops a comprehensive framework for AI governance and resilience, addressing the challenges of deploying secure, efficient, and responsible AI systems.

Cloud-Edge environments, characterized by their federated and dynamic nature, demand governance mechanisms that integrate transparency, robustness, and scalability. These mechanisms must align with ethical principles and adapt to evolving regulatory requirements, as outlined by initiatives such as the EU AI Act¹, OECD Principles², and UNESCO's recommendations on Ethics of Artificial Intelligence³.

The Horizon Europe *Cognitive Decentralised Edge Cloud (CODECO)*⁴ projects leverage these frameworks to ensure that the use of AI the CODECO framework and use-cases is handled in a transparent, trustworthy, and inclusive way, following the mentioned guiding principles.

This white paper presents **CARG**, the CODECO approach to assessing AI resilience and governance in the CODECO framework and CODECO use-cases. By introducing tools and methodologies for automating assessment, monitoring, and continuous improvement, the CODECO **CARG** framework positions itself as a blueprint for assessment of AI resilience for Edge-Cloud orchestration tools.

The white paper has been structured as follows. Section 2 explains the **CARG** principles and highlights where CODECO applies AI. Sections 3-6 explain the **CARG** dimensions. Section 7 summarises the **CARG** toolkit. Section 8 concludes the white paper.

¹ <https://artificialintelligenceact.eu/>

² <https://www.oecd.org/en/topics/sub-issues/ai-principles.html>

³ <https://www.unesco.org/en/articles/recommendation-ethics-artificial-intelligence>

⁴ <https://he-codeco.eu/>

2 CARG

CODECO relies on AI/ML approaches to support a finer-grained orchestration that takes into consideration OSI cross-layer information to provide an optimized deployment of applications across the far Edge and Cloud (Edge-Cloud). From a technical perspective, it is relevant to address how CODECO can handle heterogeneous data sets across federated, multi-architecture environments, thus reducing manual intervention, and providing the means to support a robust response to potential attacks across Cloud-Edge both during setup and runtime of applications across federated clusters.

The main goals of the proposed framework are:

- To Ensure an adequate data preparation, handling, and pre-processing.
- To propose a way to evaluate requirements regarding the robustness and resilience of CODECO use-cases.
- To ensure the capability of CODECO to answer external changes or variations of data quality in a robust way.
- To ensure CODECO transparency and explainability, as well as replicability.

2.1 Core Dimensions

The **CARG** framework is built on four core dimensions: **governance**, **resilience**, **continuous improvement**, and **assessment** as represented in Figure 1. These dimensions collectively address the challenges of deploying CODECO components or use-cases that rely on AI across the Cloud-Edge continuum.

Figure 1: CODECO AI governance and resilience methodological approach, core dimensions.

Effective **governance** of AI within CODECO is essential to ensure responsible, ethical, and transparent deployment of AI technologies. Firstly, CODECO must establish clear and comprehensive ethical principles and values to guide the development and use of AI. These principles should emphasize **fairness**, **transparency**, and **accountability**, ensuring that AI systems uphold human rights and do not perpetuate biases or inequalities. A critical aspect of

governance is the alignment of these values with existing legal and regulatory frameworks, both internal and external. These frameworks should be evaluated not only for their compliance requirements but also for their capacity to mitigate risks and promote the **responsible use** of AI technologies across all operational levels within CODECO.

AI governance in CODECO is expected to encompass the **entire lifecycle** of the applications. This includes establishing robust mechanisms for **valid data acquisition and preparation**, ensuring data is accurate, representative, and free from bias. A foundational aspect of governance is the **engagement of stakeholders**. It is important to identify how various stakeholders—ranging from developers and users to regulatory bodies and affected communities—interact with AI systems within CODECO. Stakeholders must be informed, involved, and equipped to provide feedback throughout the AI lifecycle. Furthermore, governance should proactively identify and assess foreseeable risks, such as unintended consequences or ethical dilemmas, and implement preventive and mitigative measures to ensure AI serves the proposed use-cases and society responsibly.

Transparency and explainability are vital for building trust in AI systems. CODECO must ensure that its AI solutions are developed in a way that allows for clear understanding of decision-making processes, including the identification and mitigation of potential biases. This includes the documentation of model logic, data sources, and training methodologies. Moreover, the organization should maintain dedicated processes to address concerns related to invalid, biased, or malicious data, and to respond effectively to any issues that may arise from such data influences.

Resilience considers security, robustness, as well as monitoring and evaluation. In the context of **Security and Robustness**, it is essential to assess whether AI systems used within CODECO are resilient to cyberattacks, manipulation, and adversarial inputs. Ensuring system security and maintaining data integrity requires the implementation of appropriate technical and procedural safeguards. These may include encryption, access control, anomaly detection, and robust testing frameworks, all designed to protect AI systems from both internal and external threats.

As for **monitoring and evaluation**, CODECO must be equipped to handle errors and unexpected scenarios in a manner that prevents unintended consequences and ensures system stability. AI systems should be capable of adapting to dynamic environments and learning from experience through mechanisms such as feedback loops, retraining processes, or adaptive algorithms. To support this, continuous monitoring and improvement processes must be in place to uphold the performance, reliability, and safety of AI technologies as they evolve. Moreover, the presence of clear structures for human oversight and intervention is critical. These structures help ensure that AI is applied only within appropriate boundaries and remains aligned with its intended purposes, allowing humans to retain ultimate control over automated decision-making processes.

The third dimension, **Continuous Improvement**, focuses on establishing measures that enable the responsible and resilient adaptation of AI use within CODECO. This includes responding effectively to emerging changes such as evolving datasets, shifts in operational contexts, or updates in regulatory requirements.

The last dimension, **Assessment**, focuses on the use of the proposed principles and tools to continuously evaluate the use of AI in CODECO and its impact on the CODECO assets, and also towards target stakeholder groups.

2.2 AI in CODECO

The CODECO OSS framework and its components rely on AI/ML approaches to provide a more flexible and finer-grained management (orchestration) to containerized applications from the far Edge to the Cloud. It should be highlighted that CODECO provides the infrastructure and capabilities to support applications running across the *Cloud-Edge-IoT (CEI)* continuum. AI applications are therefore in this position. AI/ML in the context of CODECO is therefore a technology enabler – CODECO is not directly related to the core functionality of AI.

In CODECO, the purpose of using AI/ML is the following:

- **Supporting real-time data processing:** a first purpose relates to real-time data processing. The data used in this process relates to the CODECO infrastructure (nodes, networks, and data workflow), and may also relate to the applications supported by CODECO, as it occurs in use-cases. The data processing is expected to occur on the Edge. For single cluster operation, it will rely on AI/ML centralized patterns; for federated clusters, it will rely on decentralized AI/ML patterns.
- **Enabling decentralized AI models:** CODECO's framework is expected to handle the deployment of AI models directly on Edge (far Edge, near Edge), which can be beneficial for applications where privacy or low latency is critical.
- **Improving Quality of Experience (QoE):** By enabling real-time data processing and decentralized AI, CODECO can contribute to a better user experience for applications that rely on AI, such as autonomous vehicles or smart factories.

Figure 2 provides an overview of the CODECO components, and where AI/ML is applied to handle specific functions. The functions are summarized as follows:

- AI/ML is used in the CODECO component **Privacy preservation Decentralized Learning (PDLC)** to provide recommendations on where application micro-services should be deployed considering the CEI infrastructure composed of nodes and links, available for specific applications.
- Estimation of a proposed placement based on target profiles provided by the user (e.g., the system should be optimized to reduce energy or to increase resilience) is sent from PDLC to the scheduler that CODECO relies upon within the **Seamless Workload Migration (SWM)** component.
- Detection of abnormal patterns, e.g., networking issues, will (second period of CODECO) be sent to the component that handles the networking aspects, **Network Management and Adaptation (NetMA)**.
- AI/ML is also used in PDLC to analyse infrastructure resource usage, thus feeding the system with predictions about future demands, and requests for a dynamic resource allocation readjustment.
- This information is made available to the user via the **Automated Configuration Management and Security (ACM)** component, and to the CODECO scheduler in SWM.
- SWM makes a weighted decision (hence, AI-driven decision) on re-scheduling allocated resources.

AI-driven decision-making in CODECO therefore optimizes application workload allocation and rescheduling based on data-compute-network metrics, e.g., latency, bandwidth, memory, processing, energy.

Figure 2: AI use in CODECO. The core AI component is PDLC, which provides an estimate on the system stability over time. PDLC provides recommendations for suitable nodes to the CODECO scheduler in SWM. Furthermore, PDLC is expected to provide in the future network state prediction.

2.3 Target Stakeholders and Use of AI in CODECO

CODECO engages a diverse range of stakeholders to ensure its platform meets real-world needs and drives broad adoption across sectors:

- **Industry & ICT Players:** Includes large tech companies and SMEs deploying Cloud-Edge Infrastructure solutions. They benefit from CODECO's orchestration tools and contribute to system integration.
- **Public Sector:** Municipalities, policy makers, and smart city planners use CODECO to simplify and scale digital public services. They are involved through use case implementations and pilot activities.
- **Standardization & Open-Source Communities:** Engage through collaborations that ensure CODECO aligns with global standards and open-source ecosystems, supporting interoperability and adoption.
- **Academia & Research:** Universities and research institutions help validate Condeco's innovations and share knowledge through research networks and partnerships.
- **End Users:** Citizens and professionals in sectors like manufacturing, energy, and smart cities interact with CODECO through use cases and the IRCEP engagement programme.
- **Developers & Early Adopters:** Software developers contribute to CODECO's evolution by testing tools, providing feedback, and participating in community-driven innovation initiatives.

3 Ethical Principles, AI Governance and Lifecycle Management

The **CARG** approach to AI governance is anchored in ethical principles such as accountability, transparency, data privacy, and adherence to FAIR principles. These values are supported by European guidelines including the GDPR, the *High-Level Expert Group (HLEG)*⁵ report, the *General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR)*⁶, and the *Artificial Intelligence Act (AIA)*⁷. AI governance in CODECO encompasses the full lifecycle of the applications — from data acquisition to deployment [1]. It includes oversight of what data is used, how models are trained, where and how they are deployed, and the continuous monitoring of their performance. Governance ensures that AI application is not only compliant but also adaptable to regulatory changes and operational needs. **CARG** considers the following lifecycle steps:

- **Data Acquisition and Management:** All data used must be catalogued, traceable, well-documented, legally compliant, and appropriately labelled. This enables transparency and accountability in model development.
- **Data Engineering:** Raw data undergoes preprocessing (e.g., cleaning, transformation) tailored to the model’s needs. These steps must be documented, along with the tools and code used.
- **Training:** The model is exposed to input-output data to learn desired behavior. Key training parameters, such as algorithms used, data sources, and energy consumption, should be logged for accountability and compliance.
- **Tuning/Alignment:** After training, models may be adjusted for specific tasks or constrained to meet ethical or operational boundaries. These constraints should be documented to ensure predictable and responsible AI behavior.
- **Evaluation and benchmarking:** AI models should be assessed against established benchmarks to determine their fitness for specific tasks. While standard, public benchmarks are ideal for common or regulated use cases, custom benchmarks may be developed for unique applications. All benchmark results must be documented with each model version to ensure transparency and traceability.
- **Risk documentation:** Any risks related to the AI model’s operation should be explicitly described. Preferably, these should be quantified (e.g., probability of producing undesired outputs). At a minimum, known risks and potential impacts must be outlined, along with appropriate mitigation strategies.
- **Standardization and Documentation:** As the AI industry evolves, tools like model cards [4] (e.g., from HuggingFace) and platforms like Kubeflow help standardize how AI models are documented, trained, and deployed. These tools support transparency by tracking performance, data inputs, resource usage, and compliance with benchmarks—essential for effective governance and lifecycle management in CODECO.

⁵ <https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/policies/expert-group-ai>

⁶ <https://gdpr-info.eu/>

⁷ <https://artificialintelligenceact.eu/>

4 Transparency, Explainability and Bias Detection

The growing complexity of AI models—particularly those using Deep Learning and Gradient Boosting—has increased the demand for explainable systems. These systems enhance transparency, foster trust, and allow stakeholders to detect and address biases or hallucinations in AI outputs. Transparent AI is essential to ensure accountability and reduce cognitive bias during decision-making.

Explainable AI (XAI) [5] provides users with insights into model behavior beyond predictions, promoting transparency and reducing errors or unintended consequences. Effective explanations should be robust, remaining consistent under input changes; Human-centric, adapted to the user's needs and technical capacity; Monitorable, enabling the quality of explanations to be objectively assessed.

The CODECO framework and its PDLC component considers XAI currently including a **Spatio-Temporal Graph Neural Network** for resource forecasting and a **Multi-Agent Reinforcement Learning model** for node ranking.

Given the two types of models at hand, we recommend using a model agnostic XAI technique to provide holistic and homogeneous explanations across the two models. The most common model agnostic XAI techniques are the following [5]:

- **Principal Components Analysis (PCA):** PCA is a traditional dimensionality reduction technique which can also be applied as an explainability method when used to identify the most relevant features that affected the outcome of an AI model. PCA works by linearly transforming data onto a new coordinate system such that the directions (principal components) capturing the largest variation in the data can be easily identified [6].
- **Local Interpretable Model-agnostic Explanations (LIME):** LIME is a model-agnostic XAI method that perturbs the input around its neighbourhood and sees how the model's predictions behave to figure out what parts of the interpretable input are contributing to the prediction. LIME weighs these perturbed data points by their proximity to the original data point and fits an interpretable model to explain the predictions. The output of LIME is a set of explanations representing the contribution of each feature to a prediction for a single sample, which is a form of local interpretability [7][8][9].

Bias in AI can stem from imbalanced or non-representative training data, leading to unfair or discriminatory outcomes. Bias detection in CODECO is crucial for promoting equity, trust, and fairness. It relies on inclusivity, involving diverse stakeholders in the assessment, ethical principles, ensuring fairness and justice and continuous improvement, refining detection methods over time.

The CODECO PDLC component integrates both monitoring data (e.g., CPU/memory usage) and context-aware data (e.g., greenness/resilience). For bias detection, CODECO uses data-type agnostic techniques, such as fair **Representation Learning**, to minimize influence from sensitive attributes and **causal Inference**, to uncover and address hidden biases in data relationships.

5 Resilience Aspects

5.1 Securing the CEI Infrastructure

The CODECO framework is designed to support containerised applications across Edge-Cloud based on an AI-driven recommendation approach. Different multiple cybersecurity threats that span the entire application lifecycle—from data collection and training to deployment and inference. Securing both the infrastructure and CODECO (AI) components is vital to ensuring integrity, reliability, and trust.

CARG classifies threats into three major categories:

- **Edge Device-Oriented Threats:** These include unauthorized access to edge nodes [9], malware injection due to limited hardware protection [10], and misuse of resources or functionalities through AI system vulnerabilities [11].
- **Data-Oriented Threats:** Data tampering [12] and theft [13] pose risks to the confidentiality and accuracy of data exchanged across distributed nodes.
- **AI Model-Oriented Threats** [14]: This includes illegal use or manipulation of AI inference outputs and adversarial attacks — particularly gradient-based techniques [15] — used to reverse-engineer models or degrade their performance.

By understanding and addressing these threats, the CODECO framework can enhance its security posture, ensuring robust protection for AI-based services and the overall CEI ecosystem. To mitigate these threats, CODECO applies a layered security strategy, including:

- **AI model encryption** (e.g., Differential Privacy [16]),
- **Data encryption** (e.g., Data Masking [17], Tokenization [18], White Noise [19]),
- **Secure data transfer protocols** (e.g., SSL, SFTP),
- **Anti-code lifting tools** (e.g., Code obfuscation and encryption [20]).

Security is further reinforced with **adversarial defence methods** tailored to CODECO's AI. These include continuous threat assessment and a structured **risk checklist** for use-cases. This checklist helps identify proximity to specific risks and provides mitigation strategies to secure the AI lifecycle.

5.2 Evaluation and Experimentation

CODECO uses a **Kubernetes-based open-source experimentation framework, CODEF**⁸ [21] designed for the Edge-Cloud continuum. Key features include:

- Declarative experiment configuration across layers and clusters,
- Automation of test setup, execution, and result visualization,
- Compatibility with tools like **Grafana K6**⁹ and **Kubeflow**¹⁰,
- Support for reproducible and modular experimentation with minimal overhead.

Currently, the CODECO experimentation framework provides the following advantages for monitoring and evaluation of AI/ML approaches over Edge-Cloud environments: i) holistic

⁸ <https://gitlab.eclipse.org/eclipse-research-labs/codeco-project/experimentation-framework-and-demonstrations>

⁹ <https://k6.io/>

¹⁰ <https://www.kubeflow.org/>

experimental definitions for all layers of the protocol stack and main K8s features, including the support of alternative edge infrastructures (e.g., choice of hypervisor and server hardware) and virtualization technologies, to accommodate the diversity of edge cloud demands, ii) appropriately designed abstractions to reduce experimentation complexity, iii) advanced automation and reliability, enabling the execution of experiments with different combinations of cross-layer parameters, that may also serve as reference points to evaluate a diverse set of intelligent algorithms, spanning from ML to optimization techniques. Along these lines, the framework also possesses additional advantages: i) reproducible experimentation with one-liner commands and versioning of components, ii) minimal operational support and risk since the deployments can be easily deleted and then re-configured, and iii) support for crucial performance metrics related to resource utilization, i.e., CPU and memory consumption.

Scalable and Real-World Evaluation

CODECO monitoring and evaluation methodology targets the following emerging concepts, regarding the applicability of the AI/ML approaches in the Edge-Cloud continuum:

Resource-Aware Performance: Evaluation

- **Scalable and Real-World Evaluation:** The approach goes beyond small-scale testing to assess how AI systems perform in real-life, large-scale deployments. It focuses on robustness, reliability, and efficiency under operational conditions, ensuring solutions are validated across CODECO's diverse use cases.

Adaptability to Heterogeneous Environments

- **Resource-Aware Performance:** Evaluation considers both model accuracy and system-level metrics such as latency, CPU/memory usage, and energy consumption. This dual focus highlights the trade-offs between algorithmic complexity and real-world constraints, especially important in resource-

Resilience and Optimization

limited environments.

- **Adaptability to Heterogeneous Environments:** Given the diversity of devices, networks, and virtualization technologies in the Edge-Cloud continuum, CODECO ensures its experimentation framework supports flexible testing across federated, distributed, and hybrid scenarios.
- **Resilience and Optimization:** The framework integrates anomaly detection and optimization techniques to proactively identify inefficiencies and dynamically reallocate resources. This supports reliable, cost-effective operations and aligns with broader goals of ethical and secure AI deployment.

6 Continuous Improvement

In the context of the CODECO project, it is imperative to ensure that AI systems are developed and deployed responsibly, adhering to ethical standards and regulatory requirements. Responsible AI aims to create systems that are fair, transparent, accountable, robust, and aligned with human values. It serves as a critical checkpoint where various aspects of data analysis, AI-based decision-making, and policy adherence are evaluated and potentially revised.

During the review phase, data analyses are scrutinized to ensure accuracy,

integrity, and compliance with established standards. This involves assessing the methodologies used, the quality of the data inputs, and the validity of the insights derived. Any discrepancies or issues identified during this process can trigger adjustments or refinements to improve the overall effectiveness of the data analysis pipeline. Moreover, the review phase extends to the examination of AI-based decisions. Here, the focus is on verifying whether the decisions made by AI models align with predefined criteria, ethical guidelines, and regulatory requirements.

Importantly, the review and adaptation process also encompass review current methods and update policies. This involves evaluating whether the existing policies and guidelines established within the CODECO framework are being effectively implemented and whether they remain relevant considering evolving technological landscapes and regulatory changes. If discrepancies or gaps are identified, adjustments to policies may be necessary to ensure alignment with current best practices and compliance standards.

Lastly, the focus on security and privacy is in line with regulatory frameworks like GDPR, stressing human oversight, technical robustness, and data governance protocols. Prioritizing these essentials for trust in AI systems while protecting individual rights and privacy.

The Table 6 outline the key aspects of responsible AI, each with a specific focus to guide the development process within the CODECO project.

7 CARG Toolkit and Assessment

The **CARG** toolkit a set of tools to assess the governance robustness, resilience, and the potential impact that the use of AI in CODECO may have on the CODECO stakeholders. AI impact assessment is the process of systematically evaluating the potential consequences, both positive and negative, of AI technologies on the various CODECO target group stakeholders. Relevant resources, including forms and templates, are available at <https://he-codeco.eu/carg>.

The assessment process in **CARG** is designed to systematically evaluate the AI governance and resilience framework using a value-chain approach. This ensures alignment with ethical standards, regulatory compliance, and stakeholder expectations.

The assessment comprises the following stages:

- **Methodology Definition:** Establishes the structured approach and principles guiding the assessment, as described in the current deliverable.
- **Data Collection:** Gathers both qualitative and quantitative data across work packages and components using standardized templates.
- **Analysis:** Interprets data to identify patterns, weaknesses, and risks in areas such as model performance, data quality, and security.
- **Evaluation:** Benchmarks CODECO' s components and use-cases against predefined criteria using a scoring template based on selected assessment criteria.
- **Reporting:** a detailed report summarizing findings, evaluations, and recommendations, leveraging a Git-based agile reporting format, is provided.
- **Feedback:** Assessment findings are presented to stakeholders for input to refine and validate conclusions.
- **Review:** Validates the process and results, incorporating feedback for final revisions.
- **Follow-up:** Translates findings into action plans to improve AI governance and resilience, followed by continuous monitoring of outcomes.

The proposed assessment criteria, scored from 1 (low) to 5 (high), with equal weighting are:

- **Quality** – Overall standard of the system or process.
- **Value Proposition** – Benefit and improvement delivered.
- **Usability** – Ease and efficiency of use.
- **Relevancy** – Applicability to current needs.
- **Transparency** – Clarity and openness of operations.
- **Compliance** – Alignment with legal and regulatory frameworks.
- **Security** – Safeguards against threats.
- **Adaptability** – Responsiveness to change.
- **Stakeholder Engagement** – Inclusion and responsiveness to users.
- **Explainability** – Understandability of AI decisions.
- **Bias Detection** – Effectiveness in identifying and mitigating biases.

8 Summary

CARG is an AI resilience and governance framework developed and being applied in the context of the HE project CODECO.

CARG is composed of a set of tools to ensure that AI-driven Cloud-Edge orchestration is transparent, ethical, resilient and secure. Through its structured AI lifecycle management, **CARG** integrates governance principles, resilience strategies, and continuous improvement mechanisms. The adoption of assessment tools such as ALTAI, real-time monitoring systems, and stakeholder engagement mechanisms enhances transparency and accountability. Furthermore, by aligning with international AI governance frameworks such as the EU AI Act, OECD Principles on AI, and UNESCO Ethics of AI, CODECO ensures that its **CARG** methodological approach remain adaptable and aligned with global best practices.

As AI technologies continue to evolve, CODECO will refine and expand its tooling set to address emerging challenges, including advanced bias detection, dynamic risk assessment, and decentralized AI models. These enhancements will further strengthen CODECO's ability to deliver privacy-preserving AI-driven orchestration across federated Cloud-Edge infrastructures.

Ultimately, CODECO contributes to the broader research community by establishing a replicable AI resilience and governance framework, considering EU principles that balance AI innovation with ethical and regulatory requirements. By fostering transparency, resilience, and adaptability, CODECO paves the way for responsible AI adoption in complex and distributed environments.

References

- [1] V. Vieira (Ed.). CODECO D2: Data Management and Ethics Handling v1.0 (1.0). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7940385>. 2023.
- [2] R. C. Sofia (Ed.) et al., R. (2024). CODECO Deliverable D10 - Technological Guidelines, Reference Architecture, and Open-source Ecosystem Design. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12819444>
- [3] Georgios, S. (Ed .) . et . al . (2024). CODECO D12 - Basic Operation Components and Toolkit version 2.0. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12819424>
- [4] M. Mitchell, Margaret, S. Wu, A. Zaldivar, P. Barnes, L. Vasserman, B. Hutchinson, E. Spitzer, I. Deborah Raji, T. Gebru. "Model cards for model reporting." In Proceedings of the conference on fairness, accountability, and transparency, pp. 220-229. 2019.
- [5] E. Tjoa and C. Guan, "A Survey on Explainable Artificial Intelligence (XAI): Toward Medical XAI," in IEEE Transactions on Neural Networks and Learning Systems, vol. 32, no. 11, pp. 4793-4813, Nov. 2021, doi: 10.1109/TNNLS.2020.3027314.
- [6] M. Tulio Ribeiro, S. Singh, C. Guestrin, "Why Should I Trust You?": Explaining the Predictions of Any Classifier. In Proceedings of the 22nd ACM SIGKDD International Conference on Knowledge Discovery and Data Mining (KDD '16). Association for Computing Machinery, New York, NY, USA, 1135–1144. 2006. <https://doi.org/10.1145/2939672.2939778>
- [7] H. Lakkaraju, E. Kamar, R. Caruana, J. Leskovec, "Faithful and Customizable Explanations of Black Box Models". In Proceedings of the 2019 AAAI/ACM Conference on AI, Ethics, and Society (AIES '19). Association for Computing Machinery, New York, NY, USA, 131–138. 2019. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3306618.3314229>.
- [8] M. Kaiser, C. Otte, T. A. Runkler, and C. H. Ek, "Interpretable dynamics models for data-efficient reinforcement learning," CoRR, vol. abs/1907.04902, pp. 2–5, Jul. 2019. [Online]. Available: <http://arxiv.org/abs/1907.04902>
- [9] P. Mahadevappa, R. Al-amri, G. Alkaws, A. A. Alkahtani, M. F. Alghenaim, M. Alsamman. Analyzing Threats and Attacks in Edge Data Analytics within IoT Environments. IoT, 5(1), 123-154. 2024.
- [10] I. Gulatas, H. H. Kilinc, A. H. Zaim, M. A. Aydin, "Malware threat on edge/fog computing environments from Internet of things devices perspective". IEEE Access, 11, 33584-33606. 2023.
- [11] A. Sohal, R. Sandhu, S. Sood, V. Chang. "A cybersecurity framework to identify malicious edge device in fog computing and cloud-of-things environments". Computers & Security. 74. 2017. DOI: 10.1016/j.cose.2017.08.016.

- [12] D. Saxena, D., V. Raychoudhury, N. SriMahathi, “SmartHealth-NDNoT: Named Data Network of Things for Healthcare Services”. In *MobileHealth@ MobiHoc* (pp. 45-50). 2015.
- [13] Y. Xiao, Y. Jia, C. Liu, X. Cheng, J. Yu, W. Lv, “Edge computing security: State of the art and challenges”. *Proceedings of the IEEE*, 107(8), 1608-1631. 2019.
- [14] J.B. Michael, J. B. Security, and privacy for edge artificial intelligence. *IEEE Security & Privacy*, 19(04), 4-7. 2021.
- [15] S. Zhou, C. Liu, D. Ye, T. Zhu, W. Zhou, P. Yu. “Adversarial attacks and defenses in deep learning: From a perspective of cybersecurity”. *ACM Computing Surveys*, 55(8), 1-39. 2022.
- [16] C. Dwork, “Differential privacy”. In *International colloquium on automata, languages, and programming* (pp. 1-12). Berlin, Heidelberg: Springer Berlin Heidelberg. 2006.
- [17] W. Bender, D. Gruhl, N. Morimoto, A. Lu, A, “Techniques for data hiding”. *IBM systems journal*, 35(3.4), 313-336. 1996.
- [18] F. Oigiau-Neamtii, “Tokenization as a data security technique”. *Zeszyty Naukowe AON*, (2 (103), 124-135. 2016.
- [19] P. Moulin, R. Koetter, “Data-hiding codes”. *Proceedings of the IEEE*, 93(12), 2083-2126. 2005.
- [20] G. Koukis, S. Skaperas, I. Kapetanidou, V. Tsaoussidis, L. Mamas, “An Open-Source Experimentation Framework for the Edge Cloud Continuum”. in *Proc. INFOCOM 2024 CNERT: Computer and Networking Experimental Research using Testbeds Workshop (CNERT)*, Vancouver, Canada. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10840008>. 2024.
- [21] G. Koukis, “Performance Evaluation of Kubernetes Networking Approaches across Constraint Edge Environments”. In *Proc. IEEE ISCC 2024 workshop ECO2024*, Paris. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11919057>. 2024.